

Analysis of Motor Cycle Helmet under Static and Dynamic Loading

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Abstract : Each year nearly nine hundred persons die in head injuries and over fifty thousand persons are severely injured due to non wearing of helmets . In motor cycle accidents, the human head is exposed to heavy impact loading against natural protection. In this work, an attempt has been made for analyzing the helmet with all the standard data. The simulation software 'ANSYS' is used to analyze the helmet with different conditions such as bottom fixed-load on top surface, bottom fixed -load on top line, side fixed -load on opposite surface, side fixed-load on opposite line and dynamic analysis. The maximum force of 19.5 kN is applied on the helmet to study the model in static and dynamic conditions. The simulation has been carried out for the static condition for the parameters like total deformation, strain energy, von- Mises stress for different cases. The dynamic analysis has been performed for the parameter like total deformation and equivalent elastic strain. The result shows that this values are concentrated in the retention portion of the helmet. These results has been compared with the standard experimental data proposed by the BIS and well within the acceptable limit.

Keywords : Helmet, deformation, strain energy, equivalent elastic strain

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